

THE STATE OF TEACHING THE COURSE “DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION” AT PRESENT TIME

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Abstract. *Digital technologies in education are becoming an integral part of the educational process. The article provides a literary overview of the state of teaching of the course "digital technologies in education". The methods and ways of mastering and applying digital technologies by scientists and teachers are considered.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, information and communication technologies, gamification, augmented and virtual reality.*

Introduction

It is important to suggest that in line with international trends, since 2020 Uzbekistan has introduced the course “Digital Technologies in Education” into the curricula of higher education institutions to train future teachers in the field of information and communication technologies. According to the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan ‘On Measures to Raise the Field of Information and Communication Technologies to a New Level in 2022-2023, a target has been set to train more than 6,500 young people annually in information technologies by developing a system for training specialists in digital technologies through distance education [2].

In this regard, researchers and educators are conducting studies and developing approaches to mastering digital technologies. M.J. Saidova is researching the use of information technologies in teaching by improving teaching methodologies [3]. In the scholarly work of I.R. Yokubova [6], methodological proposals are presented for enhancing the professional competence of future specialists through the Prezi Desktop 6.26.0 program, which enables focused study of language nuances during classroom activities. Educational technologies have been improved through the development of electronic learning resources. The author has developed the interactive program “Russian Language for Military Lawyers”, an electronic “Russian-Uzbek-English Dictionary of Legal Terms”, and the electronic textbook “Fascinating Russian Language”.

“A.A. Ikramov [7] proposes the use of information and communication technologies in his work to improve teaching methods through students’ engagement with physical (active) games in learning, the use of active teaching methods such as role-playing games that help students master the study material more deeply, and the application of gamification to increase students’ interest in the subject.

D.S. Sarimova [8], in her research, proposes her own method of using information and communication technologies to improve the instructional and methodological competence of chemistry teachers within the professional development system. It is proposed that virtual and augmented reality be used in the learning process. The use of virtual reality in laboratory classes enables students to conduct experiments that cannot be carried out in real life and would be dangerous. The use of augmented reality makes it possible to create interactive teaching aids that make the learning material more interesting and more visual.

In her research, M.I. Akhmedova [9] has developed and implemented, using information technologies, an “Uzbek-Latin-Russian-English Electronic Medical Dictionary”. This dictionary was compiled based on findings related to the development of professional communicative literacy in English among medical students.”

As a result, the level of professional, grammatical, and phonetic competence among medical students has significantly increased through English language instruction. It is important to emphasize the effectiveness of the specially designed English language training system, which is complemented by an electronic dictionary, interactive audio tools, and multimedia resources. Enhancing the course with relevant video materials and interactive simulations greatly strengthens the students’ comprehension of the studied material.

Based on information and communication technologies, I.R. Choriev [10] developed recommendations for the pedagogical design of professional development processes. A model has been created for the formation and development of readiness for pedagogical design using information and communication technologies; the pedagogical factors for its application have been specified; the algorithmic procedures for training teaching staff for project activities based on information technologies have been modernized; and methods have been developed to improve the effectiveness of pedagogical design activities.

In the field of higher education, regarding the development of experimental knowledge through the use of educational software, P.M. Jalalova [11] has proposed recommendations for the effective use of information technologies in laboratory classes and optimized the step-by-step implementation of experimental and virtual exercises in “Atomic Physics”. A methodology has been presented for developing students’ creative abilities through a specially designed set of pedagogical elements for classroom instruction; instructional and methodological support for laboratory classes has been proposed; and, based on the evaluation of learning outcomes using laboratory developments, educational software has been improved to support the formation of professional competencies in future physics specialists

“In her research, D.A. Zaripova [12] examines the improvement of the system for preparing students for innovative activities in the field of vocational education within the context of the informatization of higher education through the introduction of Smart methods, Smart portfolios, and the Chalk and Talk approach. The content of student training has been enhanced through the development of the Network Boomerang technology and methods for its use. Electronic learning resources based on the Network Boomerang technology have been created and implemented using PHP, the Laravel framework, and JavaScript, all aimed at developing students’ innovative activities in the field of vocational education. Methodologies for Smart, Smart portfolios, the Network Boomerang technology, and its mobile version have been developed to foster students’ innovative activities in vocational education and have been integrated into the teaching process at higher education institutions.

T.T. Kalekeeva [13] explores the application of information technologies in education by improving the content of professional training for future computer science teachers. She developed a modernized process for building information literacy and preparedness, proposed a detailed methodology for teaching computer science based on enhancing pedagogical capacities in educational institutions, and, as a result, supported the development of professional competence. Scientifically substantiated proposals have been presented with the aim of optimizing the training content for future computer science teachers.”

“A similar topic was developed by M.Kh. Ikramova [14] in her research on improving the methodology for developing the professional competence of future teachers, using the example of teaching the subject “Technology” and applying digital educational resources in the learning process.

Based on digital technologies, F.F. Kasimov [15] researched and developed a methodology for forming programming skills among students and proposed ways of using digital technologies to increase the level of mastery of educational material and develop programming skills. An educational process model has been optimized, justified by a methodology that determines the level and degree of mastery of programming skills. Methods for developing programming skills in students have been proposed, and a teaching methodology has been constructed using technologies aimed at designing an algorithm for mastering programming languages while fostering students’ creative abilities in programming.

In the context of digitalization, N.Sh. Mavlyanov [16] proposed an innovative methodology for developing the information competence of preschool education teachers. He analyzed the current state and problems of using information and communication technologies to raise the level of teachers’ qualifications and suggested solutions, along with opportunities for developing the information competence of preschool educators. A digital platform has been developed and tested in practice, designed specifically to develop the information competence of preschool education teachers.

In the scientific research of P. Svyard [3], the possibilities of managing digital information content through a higher education institution’s information system are presented consistently, thoroughly, and concretely. In the work of K. White [2], the technology of distance learning is defined.”

“The development of skills for organizing distance learning is discussed by M. Claro, Salinas, and T. Cabello-Hutt [5] in their scholarly work ‘Learning in a Digital Environment,’ in which they analyzed the testing of pedagogical skills and abilities of Chilean teachers in teaching students methods for solving information and communication tasks in a digital environment.

All of the above-mentioned scholars, in their research, demonstrate and emphasize the unique opportunities that modern digital technologies offer for education. They highlight the urgent need for and relevance of contemporary levels of computer literacy for professionals in all fields and sectors of our lives.

In their research, M. Schultz and K. Scholz [4] note that, with the help of computer technologies, it is now possible to gather information about the learning process and its trajectory and to conduct a rating analysis of learning outcomes. By mastering and applying modern digital technologies, it becomes possible to design an individualized learning path. Students and teachers have gained unlimited opportunities to develop and share their educational environment collaboratively.

Despite the enormous potential of digital technologies, which are in high demand in education, they are not being fully utilized. This is due to the insufficient level of digital literacy among teachers, which leads to the emergence of a digital divide and the need to overcome it.”

Conclusion

By summarizing the mentioned above ideas it is important to mention that ensuring training and the ability to use the potential of digital technologies is a pressing objective of the course “Digital Technologies in Education.”

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